

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF NEUROMUSCULAR SCOLIOSIS IN SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY: ANESTHESIOLOGICAL CHALLENGES AND CLINICAL INSIGHTS

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Introduction: Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) is a genetic disorder characterized by progressive muscle function loss, often leading to neuromuscular scoliosis and chronic respiratory insufficiency which is the reason for surgical correction. Surgical correction of neuromuscular scoliosis in children with SMA requires a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach. This paper emphasizes the importance of anesthesiology strategies and advocates for further research to advance therapeutic interventions.

Case Report: A nine-year-old boy diagnosed with SMA and neuromuscular scoliosis underwent surgical correction. A multidisciplinary team recommended surgery, starting with opioid and hypnotic administration to replace the tracheal cannula and achieve general anesthesia. Due to challenges in urinary catheter placement, an arterial cannula, central venous catheter, nasogastric tube, and cystostomy were inserted. Neurophysiological monitoring ensured safe surgery under total intravenous anesthesia (TIVA) with propofol and remifentanyl, requiring early vasoactive support. Intraoperative blood conservation techniques (cell saver) were used alongside appropriate fluid resuscitation, including 15 ml/kg of blood, 10 ml/kg of fresh frozen plasma, 5 ml/kg of 5% albumin, and 50 ml/kg of crystalloids. Postoperatively, he was admitted to the Intensive Care Unit for mechanical ventilation, analgosedation, and minimal vasoactive support. Sedation and vasoactive support were discontinued on the first postoperative day, and he stabilized on PSV ventilation with nutrition initiated via PEG. A left-sided pneumothorax on the second day required thoracic drainage, achieving complete respiratory stability. He transitioned to the Orthopedics Department on the eighth day post-surgery after thoracic drain removal, with the cystostomy removed on the eleventh day. After three weeks in hospital, he was discharged for home care.

Discussion: Managing surgical interventions for neuromuscular scoliosis poses significant challenges for anesthesiology, including artificial ventilation and hemodynamic instability. Future research should prioritize investigating long-term outcomes, exploring innovative technologies, and refining multidisciplinary approaches to optimize clinical results and enhance the quality of life for children with SMA.